

Synthesis of novel $\text{CuFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{MIL-53}(\text{Fe})/\text{MoS}_2$ ternary heterojunction nanocomposite sonocatalytic for the degradation of organic dye pollutants

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Abstract

Supporting of CuFe_2O_4 nanoparticles and MIL-53(Fe) metal organic framework on the MoS_2 nanoflowers were successfully carried out to enhance the sonocatalytic activity using a facile ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal route. The FESEM/EDAX, XRD, FTIR, VSM, and BET were used to characterize the nanocomposite. The as-synthesized $\text{CuFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{MIL-53}(\text{Fe})/\text{MoS}_2$ sonocatalyst nanocomposite revealed a relatively high sonocatalytic activity than CuFe_2O_4 , MIL-53(Fe) and MoS_2 under H_2O_2 -ultrasonic (US) system for the degradation of organic dye pollutants, including methylene blue (MB), rhodamine B (RhB) and methyl orange (MO). Besides, the impact of several parameters such as contact time, catalyst dosage, initial concentration of MB, H_2O_2 concentration, organic dye type, and process type on the degradation reactions of MB, RhB, and MO were implemented. The obtained outcomes displayed that the $\text{CuFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{MIL-53}(\text{Fe})/\text{MoS}_2$ sonocatalytic can be degrade the MB dye (25 mg/L) up to 98.9%. The $\cdot\text{OH}$ free radicals were also recognized as the main reactive oxygen species within the MB sonodegradation reaction. Additionally, the results of the recyclability investigation of the $\text{CuFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{MIL-53}(\text{Fe})/\text{MoS}_2$ sonocatalytic obviously illustrated a less than 5% drop of the catalytic performance up to five sequential cycles. Ultimately, a proposed mechanism for the sonodegradation process of organic dyes was suggested and discussed.

Keywords: $\text{CuFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{MIL-53}(\text{Fe})/\text{MoS}_2$, nanocomposite, sonocatalyst, organic dyes, sonodegradation.